

PHARMACOLOGICAL PROSPECTS OF 2-AMINOBENZIMIDAZOLES: ADVANCES IN CHEMISTRY, SYNTHESIS, AND THERAPEUTIC POTENTIAL: A REVIEW

Maria Shafaqat¹, Sadia Awan², Abu Sulman³, Syeda Rimsha Gillani⁴, Hafsa Sehar⁵,
Waleed Maqbool⁶, Maha⁷, Khaizran Fatima Kamal⁸, Amina Afaq⁹, Hammad Mustafa¹⁰,
Muhammad Saad Naeem¹¹, Hafiz Aamir Ali Kharl^{*12}

^{1,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,*12}Department of Pharmacy, Faculty of Health and Pharmaceutical Sciences, University of
Agriculture Faisalabad, Pakistan.

²Health Services Academy, Islamabad

^{*12}aamirkharl43@gmail.com

Corresponding Author: *

Hafiz Aamir Ali Kharl

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17646843>

Received
11 September 2025

Accepted
23 October 2025

Published
19 November 2025

ABSTRACT

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2-ABI) derivatives represent a promising class of nitrogen-containing heterocycles with diverse therapeutic potential. Introduction of an amino group at the 2-position of the benzimidazole ring enhances solubility, chemical stability, and biological interactions, making these compounds attractive scaffolds in drug discovery. Owing to their structural similarity with nucleotides and natural biomolecules, 2-ABIs exhibit strong affinity toward multiple biological targets through hydrogen bonding and π - π interactions. A wide spectrum of pharmacological activities has been reported, including antimicrobial, antimalarial, antiparasitic, antileishmanial, anticancer, anti-inflammatory, anticholinesterase, cardioprotective, and neuroprotective effects. Structure Activity Relationship (SAR) studies indicate that strategic substitutions on the benzimidazole nucleus markedly influence potency and selectivity, thereby guiding rational drug design. Several marketed drugs and investigational candidates incorporate the 2-ABI core, highlighting its clinical relevance. Synthetic strategies for 2-ABIs, ranging from classical condensation to modern metal-free protocols, provide efficient access to novel analogs. Continued exploration of their molecular mechanisms and optimization of lead compounds could accelerate their progression from bench to bedside, positioning 2-ABIs as valuable scaffolds in modern pharmaceutical sciences.

Keywords: 2-Aminobenzimidazole, Pharmacological properties, Structure Activity Relationship, Scaffolds.

INTRODUCTION

The principal objective of this study is to explore the pharmacological importance of 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives which are emerging heterocyclic compounds in the field of pharmaceutical chemistry because of their therapeutic characteristics, and researchers are continuously studying and investigating these compounds for their extraordinary pharmacological potential.

Heterocyclic compounds are those cyclic organic compounds which have one or more atoms other than carbon (heteroatom) in their ring structure. The most common heteroatoms are nitrogen (N), oxygen (O), and sulfur (S). Heterocyclic compounds are the most important compounds in organic chemistry due to their diverse activities in biological fields. Biomolecules like deoxyribonucleic acid

(DNA), ribonucleic acid (RNA), chlorophyll, hemoglobin, vitamins, and a lot of other molecules contain heterocycles as a part of their skeleton. According to the database of FDA approved drugs, about 59% small-molecule drugs contain nitrogen heterocycle moieties [1,2,3]. They are commonly used as pharmaceutical agents, herbicidal substances, and veterinary medicinal products. They also serve as developers, corrosion preventive, antioxidants, sanitizers, copolymers, and pigment stuff. These compounds are also employed as mediums in the synthesis of other organic compounds. Some natural occurring products, for example, antimicrobials (penicillin's and cephalosporin), alkaloids (vinblastine, reserpine, and morphine) etc also contain heterocycles in their structures [4].

Aminobenzimidazoles are bipolar structure-containing heterocyclic aromatic compounds and characterized as the organic compounds in which benzene ring is combined with the imidazole ring with amino group (NH_2) attached at any position. If amino group replaced hydrogen and attached at position two of benzimidazole ring, resulting compound will be 2-aminobenzimidazole [5,6,7].

Hobrecker reported the first synthesis of aminobenzimidazole derivatives in 1872. These derivative compounds attract scientists because of their special geometrical properties and nucleophilic environments, which make them able to bind with several biological targets. The first research paper on the antibacterial properties of aminobenzimidazoles was published by Goodman and Nancy Hart in 1943 and by Woolley in 1944. For many years, these derivatives have been investigated for

many therapeutic activities such as antiviral, antifungal, and anticancer activities [8].

Amination (introduction of $-\text{NH}_2$ group) of benzimidazole ring enhances its miscibility in polar solvents by enhancing its polarity. High solubility further enhances its bioavailability in biological systems. Benzimidazole moiety is famous for its chemical stability due to its aromatic structure. This chemical stability is essential for its strength in biological and storage conditions. Introduction of amino group in benzimidazole ring enhances its reactivity especially in hydrogen bond and π - π interactions that are responsible for binding with biological targets and playing role in biological activity of benzimidazole [9,10,11].

These compounds are commonly used in medicinal chemistry and have broad range of pharmaceutical, industrial and education importance due to their multiple activities [12]. They also have biological and clinical significance due to their similarity with nucleotides of the living system. Their heterocyclic nature and electron-rich environment make them useable not only in the field of drug discovery but also in clinical remedies with significant therapeutic efficacy. Their nucleus is also present in natural occurring compounds like Vitamin B_{12} , having structure like purine bases [13]. Many derivative compounds of benzimidazole including aminobenzimidazole, have been researched for antiviral activity against HIV, HBV, HCV, HSV, Rota virus, Herpes virus, Coxsackie, PRSV, adenovirus and mosquito larvae. They contain antimicrobial, antimalarial, anti-ulcer and anti-tumor activity. They also have corrosion inhibition characteristics [14-29].

Fig 1. Marketed drugs containing 2-Aminobenzimidazole nucleus

There are about thirty derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole 1 documented as drugs having various therapeutic properties such as antifungal, antiviral, antiparasitic and anti-allergic and their structural properties,

synthesis and biological activities have been published [30,31]. These compounds also form complexes with metals such as zinc, copper and cobalt showing antibacterial and antifungal characteristics [32].

2. Synthesis of 2-aminobenzimidazole

2.1 Using cyanamide

2-aminobenzimidazole is obtained by ring closure of o-phenylenediamine with cyanogen bromide. The process involves the chemical reaction of o-phenylenediamine and cyanamide in the availability of protonic acid, usually at elevated temperature, resulting in the formation of 2-aminobenzimidazole (desired product).

2.2 Using Mercuric Oxide

This process of synthesis of 2-aminobenzimidazole comprising ring-closing an N-(o-amino phenyl) thiourea with mercuric oxide and desired product is obtained [33].

2.3 Halogenation of ketone with Guanidine

A new strategy of 2-aminobenzimidazole synthesis is reported in which reaction occurs between α -halogenated cyclohexanone and

guanidine. It gives facile N-bromosuccinimide (NBS) related transition metal free, viable process to produce azoles having substitution at 2-position. N-bromosuccinimide promotes direct halogenation of cyclohexyl ketone along with Oxone, which further reacts with guanidine and gives 2-aminobenzimidazoles [34].

2.4 Cascade Reaction

An efficient cascade reaction to produce 2-ABI from isoselenocyanates include the crystallization of elemental selenium (Se) from the chemical mixture much refines the purification procedure and let it to be re-utilized for synthesis of isoselenocyanates [35]. A simple method of synthesis of 2-(alkylamino) benzimidazoles involves dipeptide analog in which the guanidine functional group, (R-NH)(R'-NH)C=N-R" of an arginine has been displaced with a 2-ABI [36].

Fig 2. Different strategies for synthesis of 2-Aminobenzimidazole

3. Biological Activities

Biological activities of 2-Aminobenzimidazole reported are summarized in **Table 1**.

3.1 Antimicrobial Activity

A series of new benzimidazole derivatives having sulfides and carbamoyl esters structures, was produced using 2-aminobenzimidazole as starting material with

the yield of 16.7% to 36.4%. Their architecture was described by proton and carbon nuclear magnetic resonance (^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR). These derivatives were investigated for their antibiotic properties and results of bioassay showed that some derivatives possess potent antifungal activity and may be used to develop potential antifungal medicines [37].

2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives are potent inhibitors of density-dependent signaling against wild-type *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. In the study forty 1,2,3-triazole derivatives of 2-ABI were designed, synthesized, and described by Infrared (IR) spectroscopy, Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy (NMR), Mass spectroscopy (MS) and elemental analysis. All synthesized derivatives were investigated for ex vivo activity of density-dependent signaling inhibition against *P. aeruginosa*. Schrodinger Glide software was used for molecular docking study of the synthesized derivatives at the target biological site, LasR receptor [38]. The study reported that 2-ABI derivatives block *Salmonella enterica* serovar *Typhimurium* biofilm formation in minute strengths (μM). Moderations at different sites of hit synthesized compound produced novel potent derivatives that block *Salmonella typhimurium* biofilm development while being harmless to bacterioplankton (bacterial component of plankton, which are microscopic organisms that drift in aquatic environments) growth [39].

3.2 Antileishmanial Activity

Leishmaniasis is an infectious disorder that impacts numerous people annually. Antileishmanial medicines are used to treat it, but they have complications such as toxicity and long course therapy. *Leishmania infantum* was investigated with a compound library of 1.8 million therapeutic compounds which are freely available for this motive as segment of method development. Among these compounds, a derivative of 2-aminobenzimidazole was nominated hits, which had moderate affinity, poor metabolic lability, and high lipophilicity. Further steps of synthesis were taken to introduce different molecular fragments likely to lower lipophilicity to increase clearance and other active biological compounds with improved ex-vivo characteristics and therapeutic properties against various strains of the parasite. Elevated leptodermic activity of a compound was recorded. Among synthesized compounds, two were further used in the in-vivo acute *Leishmania infantum* VL mouse model. These compounds contained good in-vitro efficacy, but their potency and bioavailability were low

in in-vivo models which cause complexities in use of these compounds as efficient treatments. The mechanism of action of these compounds is ongoing testing, but it was recently approved that acyl (RCO-) aminobenzimidazoles may have the kinetochore CDC-like kinase-1 (CLK1) protein kinase as the main biological target [40]. Recent research showed the activity of 2-aminobenzimidazole moiety against *Trypanosoma cruzi* and *Trypanosoma brucei*, indicating wide antiparasitic characteristics [41].

3.3 Anti-H₃ Receptor Activity

2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives have been outlined as a new class of H₃ receptor antagonists which consist of 2-ABI nucleus linked to an imidazole ring structure via di- or tri-methylene spacers. These derivatives have high affinity towards the receptor that depends upon the methylene chain spacer length. 5(6)-methoxy had a sub-nanomolar binding affinity, hence indicating an extensive affinity to H₃ receptor. According to quantitative structure-activity relationship (QSAR) modeling, it was discovered that, lipophilicity (log P) and basicity (pKa) of the derivatives, is directly proportional to the compounds' receptor affinity but has a U-shaped relationship with log P. Different substitutes at position 5(6) of the benzimidazole moiety contained effect on their lipophilicity and basicity that impact their affinity towards the H₃ receptor. Intrinsically, there is a hope that derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole may be utilized as efficient H₃ receptor antagonists and may be specifically useful in cases where enhanced level of neurotransmitter release is required such as cognitive disorders [42].

3.4 Antimalarial Activity

The 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives with a N1-substituted phenol are a novel series of compounds having less toxicity and potent in-vitro activity against *Plasmodium falciparum* malaria, good ligand-lipophilicity efficiency (LLE), low metabolic stability, low MW, and synthetic tractability were their attractive pharmacological properties [43].

3.5 Antiparasitic Activity

The class of 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives was identified in a GSK (GlaxoSmithKline) compound library by using HTS (High-throughput screening) technology to generate new libraries of active compounds that have activity against trypanosomiasis and leishmaniasis [44,45,46]. Further, optimization studies as per criteria for the development of most emerging compounds, tested for ADMET (absorption, digestion, metabolism, excretion, toxicity) and antiparasitic efficacy. One derivative showed potent activity against *Trypanosoma cruzi* and *Trypanosoma brucei* and it

had good permeability, no discernible toxicity on HepG2 and MRC-5 cell lines [47].

3.6 Anticancer activity

Two new small compounds containing 2-aminobenzimidazole moiety, MFBre and MFB [1-(4-chlorobenzyl)-2-(5-methyl-2-furfurylideneamino)-benzimidazole], were synthesized and their angiostatic characteristics were tested because of their capacity as a lead compound in medicinal chemistry. Results showed that the second compound had good Anti-Angiogenic and Anti-Lymphangiogenic properties [48].

Fig 3. Therapeutic activities of 2-aminobenzimidazole

3.7 Anti-inflammatory Activity

In the research novel, acetamide derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole were synthesized and their anti-arthritis activity was investigated in rats. These derivatives were described by FTIR (Fourier transform infrared spectroscopy) and NMR (Nuclear magnetic resonance). Anti-inflammatory activity of synthesized

compounds at different strengths (10, 20 and 30 mg/kg) were tested using Carrageen-induced paw edema model. Further, most effective strengths of these compounds were tested in complete Freund's adjuvant (CFA)-induced arthritis model. The effect on inflammatory arthritis was investigated through different tests such as Reverse Transcription quantitative

Polymerase Chain Reaction (RT-qPCR) analysis, radiographic, histopathological, and hematological analysis. The synthesized derivatives show good anti-inflammatory activity as well as they decrease level of autoantibodies in body and restore hematological specifications therefore showed improved drug profile than standard drug, methotrexate. Two compounds show string inhibitory activity against pro-inflammatory mediators and according to results, they have potent anti-arthritis activity [49].

The study reported that 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives selectively inhibit NOD1 (Nucleotide-binding oligomerization domain-containing protein-1), which is an intracellular protein that acts as a pattern recognition receptor (PRR) in the natural immunity. Process-oriented study of Nodinitib-1 (prototypical drug) showed that 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives change NOD1 subcellular targeting in cells by making conformational changes of NOD1 in vitro. These derivatives give lead compounds for investigating mode regulating NOD1 activity and tools for researching the roles of NOD1 in several inflammatory and infectious disorders [50].

3.8 Anticholinesterase Activity

A series of derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole was prepared by using microwave irradiation method and their biological activity on acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase, was investigated. Some of these compounds showed potent inhibitory activity and results indicated these compounds as emerging selective blockers of AChE and BuChE and beneficial in the pharmacological management of neurodegenerative disorders [51].

3.9 Cardioprotective Activity

Some halide derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole were synthesized and investigated for their effect on cardiovascular system. One of them exhibited potent Na^+/H^+ exchanger isoform-1 (NHE-1) inhibitory activity even better than standard drug, Zoniporidone and two compounds improved heart refractory period and decreased platelets aggregation even better than standard drugs, pentoxifylline and etmosine. One of these compounds increased

heart refractory period and decreased platelets aggregation as well as suppressed glycation end products (like standard drug, aminoguanidine) [52].

3.10 Immunotropic Activity

In this study novel compounds were synthesized by reacting 2-aminobenzimidazole moiety with many acids and ketones and their biological impact on immune system was investigated in mice. One synthesized derivative decreased production of antibodies (humoral response) at specific doses but improved cell-body immunity. It reduced humoral response only at higher concentration. Another derivative also showed immunosuppressant activity. Although it had lower activity than standard drug, Cyclosporin A, it suppressed immune response in all tests efficiently [53].

3.11 Ion channel modulators

Electric potential is conducted through Ca^{2+} -activated K^+ channels that cause action potential and take part in excitation of neurons and regulation of transmission of conductivity through synapses. Inhibitors of these channels can be proved as novel therapeutic agents for neurological and psychiatric disorders such as anxiety, depression, Parkinson's disease, and cognitive disorders. Study reveals that 2-(N-substituted)-2-ABIs are better potent inhibitors of SK channels than common inhibitors as they do not block channels' pores (but they did not displace apamin in binding investigation). These inhibitors showed first example negative modulator of channel gating for blockage of Calcium-activated potassium channels, as a mechanism of action. One of these compounds causes reversible inhibition of SK3-mediated electrical conductivity with a K_d value of 9 nM [54].

3.12 Enzyme Inhibitory activity

A series of new derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole were designed, synthesized and Fragment-based drug discovery (FBDD) work was done by using 2-aminobenzimidazole moiety as original fragment. FBDD has been commonly utilized in the study of aspartyl protease inhibitors, and it showed that 2-ABI make bond with aspartyl dyad (Asp 32 and Asp 228) of BACE-1 (β -site

Amyloid precursor protein Cleaving Enzyme-1). FRET (Fluorescence resonance energy transfer) assay's result showed that among twelve synthesized 2-AMI derivatives, three could cause more than 50% enzymatic potency inhibition of BACE-1 at dose of 10 μ M. Molecular docking study revealed that 2-ABI could form many hydrogen bonds and fill S1/S2' pockets well [55].

2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives along with some other imidazole ring containing compounds, also possess varying degrees of antithyroid activity [56].

3.14 Anticonvulsant activity

2-aminobenzimidazole also secured the experimental animals against hyperbaric oxygenation convulsions at various concentrations [57].

3.13 Antithyroid activity

Table 1. Biological activities of 2-Aminobenzimidazole reported

Sr. No	Biological Activity Reported	Structure & Name	Citation
1.	Antimicrobial Activity	<p>Ethyl(6-(methylthio)-2-benzoimidazol-2-yl)carbamate</p>	37
		<p>N-(1H-benzol[d]imidazol-2-yl)-4-methyl-1H-1,2,3-triazole-1-carboxamide</p>	38
		<p>N-(2-amino-1-(3-phenylpropyl)-1H-benzol[d]imidazol-5-yl)benzamide</p>	39
2.	Antileishmanial Activity	<p>2-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(1-propyl-1H-benzol[d]imidazol-2-yl)acetamide</p>	40,41
3.	Anti-H ₃ Receptor Activity	<p>2-(1H-benzol[d]imidazol-2-yl)-N-(1H-imidazol-5-yl)acetamide</p>	42

		N-(2-(1H-imidazol-5-yl)ethyl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-amine	
4.	Antimalarial Activity		43
5.	Antiparasitic Activity	2-(2-amino-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-1-yl)phenol	44,45, 46, 47
6.	Anticholinesterase Activity	2-(4-chlorophenyl)-N-(1-propyl-1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)acetamide	51
7.	Immunotropic Activity	2-(2,3-dimethylpiperidin-1-yl)-1H-benzo[d]imidazole	53
		4-((1H-benzo[d]imidazol-2-yl)amino)-4-phenylbutan-2-one	

4. SAR Analysis

To investigate the significance of 2-aminobenzimidazole and N1-phenol relationship, different changes were made into 2-ABI nucleus to assess its comparative significance for potency. The modifications which were made are: a) Phenol substitution, modification, and replacement; b) Amino group modification and replacement; c) evaluation of divergent scaffolds.

a. Phenol substitution, modification, and replacement

Loss of Activity: Shifting hydroxyl (-OH) to meta position, substituting with amino (-NH₂),

methoxy (-OCH₃), hydroxymethyl (-CH₂OH), fluoro (-F) groups at ortho position lose its biological activity. Expanding the ring to benzofuran/indole or introducing heteroaromatic substitutes also destroys therapeutic activity.

Position effects: Substitution at 3-, 4-, 5- and 6-position highly affect the activity.

Synergistic Disubstitution: 4,5-dimethyl has potent effect but 4,6-dimethyl has comparable low effect.

Phenolic pKa correlation: A lower pKa value of the compound eliminates its activity.

Fig 4. SAR of 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives

b. Amino group modification and replacement

Removal: Removal or replacement of amino group with any other heteroatom, destroy the activity.

Scaffold change: If scaffold is changed it becomes inactive.

N-alkylation: Although substitution of branched chain shows better activity than straight chain, alkylation decreases the activity of parent compound.

c. Divergent Scaffolds

Scaffold variations or heteroaryl substitution eliminate therapeutic activity despite retaining basic patterns [58].

5. Discussion

2-Aminobenzimidazole (2-ABI) derivatives have emerged as an exceptionally versatile class of heterocyclic scaffolds with diverse pharmacological applications. A critical analysis of the reported literature highlights their structural adaptability, ability to form hydrogen bonds and π - π interactions, and resemblance to naturally occurring purine bases, which collectively contribute to their high affinity toward multiple biological targets.

From a synthetic standpoint, 2-ABI can be efficiently obtained through various strategies, including condensation of o-phenylenediamine with cyanamide, thiourea derivatives, or halogenated ketones with guanidine. The availability of cascade reactions and environmentally benign methods further broadens their synthetic accessibility. These approaches enable incorporation of structural diversity, which is essential for optimizing biological activity.

In terms of biological potential, 2-ABI derivatives demonstrate a remarkably broad spectrum of activities ranging from antimicrobial, antiparasitic, and antimalarial to anticancer, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective effects. Of particular importance is their role as quorum sensing inhibitors, enzyme blockers, ion channel modulators, and H3 receptor antagonists. Such diversity underscores the scaffold's ability to interact with targets in infectious, inflammatory, neurological, and metabolic disorders. Furthermore, the discovery of cardioprotective, immunomodulatory, and enzyme inhibitory activities positions 2-ABI as a promising nucleus for multifunctional drug design.

The SAR studies reveal that the amino group at position-2 of the benzimidazole ring is indispensable for activity, as its removal or replacement leads to a sharp decline in potency. Phenolic substitution patterns significantly influence bioactivity, with modifications at specific positions either enhancing or abolishing activity. Importantly, lipophilicity and basicity show a direct relationship with receptor affinity, particularly in H3 antagonists, while excessive alkylation or scaffold replacement tends to reduce biological relevance. These insights provide a rational framework for designing future derivatives with enhanced selectivity and potency.

Despite promising results, several challenges remain. Many reported derivatives display limited metabolic stability, poor bioavailability, or dose-dependent toxicity in in-vivo models. While some compounds show potent in-vitro efficacy, translation into clinically effective agents remains underexplored. Moreover, a lack of systematic ADMET profiling and clinical correlation restricts their progression from laboratory findings to therapeutic use.

Looking forward, the integration of computational approaches such as molecular docking, molecular dynamics simulations, QSAR, and pharmacophore modeling can accelerate the identification of potent lead molecules. Additionally, incorporation of green synthetic methods, structural hybridization, prodrug strategies, and advanced delivery systems (e.g., nanoparticles, liposomes, and polymer conjugates) may overcome pharmacokinetic limitations. The unique versatility of 2-ABI derivatives suggests they may serve as privileged scaffolds for the next generation of anti-infective, anti-inflammatory, and neuroprotective agents.

6. Conclusion

2-aminobenzimidazoles have significant importance in educational field and pharmaceutical industry. They are attractive compounds in the field of drug design, discovery and development, and various researchers are studying them, and hence large data is available on their in-vivo and ex-vivo activities. Their methods of synthesis are also simple. In contrast to many other emerging heterocyclic compounds which have more than

one step synthesis, they have one-step synthetic methods with high yield. These derivatives are emerging compounds in the field of medicinal chemistry due to having strong pharmacodynamic and pharmacokinetic characteristics. They show several biological activities such as antibacterial, antifungal, antimalarial, antiparasitic, anti-helminthic, anticonvulsant, anti-ulcer, anti-inflammatory, antileishmanial, anticholinesterases, anticancer, antithyroid, anti H3 receptor, immunotropic, cardioprotective, enzyme inhibiting and ion channels modulating activities. They are encouraged to use various diseases including neurodegenerative, cardiovascular, and psychiatric. They showed activity in animals as well as humans.

Researchers are working on these compounds so that novel compounds can be synthesized by making modifications and substitutions at distinct positions. 2-aminobenzimidazole nucleus is also present in some medicines that are available in market are commonly being used. There are expectations that some most potent compounds can be proved through clinical trials in the near future.

Author Contributions:

Conceptualization, Hafiz Aamir Ali Kharl. and Maria Shafaqat ; methodology, .; validation, X.X., Y.Y. and Z.Z.; investigation, Waleed Maqbool, Maha; resources, Khaizran Fatima Kamal.; data curation, Muhammad Saad Naeem.; writing original draft preparation, Abu Sulman.; writing review and editing, Hafiz Aamir Ali Kharl.; visualization, Syeda Rimsha Gillani, Hafsa Sehar.; supervision, Hafiz Aamir Ali Kharl.; project administration, Amina Afaq.. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding:

This research received no external funding.

Informed Consent Statement:

Not applicable

Acknowledgments:

The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to all researchers whose valuable work and insights contributed to the preparation of this review. We also acknowledge the support of our institution and colleagues for their encouragement and guidance throughout the

compilation of this manuscript. Any shortcomings in this work are solely the responsibility of the authors.

Conflicts of Interest:

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

REFERENCES

1. Nic, M., Hovorka, L., Jirat, J., Kosata, B., & Znamenacek, J. (2005) IUPAC compendium of chemical terminology—the gold book. *International Union of Pure and Applied Chemistry*. <https://doi.org/10.1351/goldbook.H02798>
2. Vitaku, E., Smith, D. T., & Njardarson, J. T. (2014) Analysis of the structural diversity, substitution patterns, and frequency of nitrogen heterocycles among US FDA approved pharmaceuticals: miniperspective. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 57(24), 10257-10274. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm501100b>
3. Gupta, M. (2015) Heterocyclic compounds and their biological significance: A Review. *International Journal of Physical, Chemical and Mathematical Sciences*, 4(1), 21-24. ISSN: 2278-683X (Jan–June 2015)
4. Arora, P., Arora, V., Lamba, H. S., & Wadhwa, D. (2012) Importance of heterocyclic chemistry: A review. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 3(9), 2947. ISSN: 0975-8232
5. Mahmood, K., Akhter, Z., Asghar, M. A., Mirza, B., Ismail, H., Liaqat, F., & McKee, V. (2020) Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluation of novel benzimidazole derivatives. *Journal of Biomolecular Structure and Dynamics*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07391102.2019.1617783>
6. Yerragunta, V., Gayathri, R., Srujana, S., Srujana, S., Devi, R., & Divya, A. Benzimidazole derivatives and its biological importance: a review. *PharmaTutor* 2014, 2(3), 109-113. ISSN 2347-7881
7. Kalhor, M., Samiei, S., & Mirshokraei, S. A. (2019). Facile one-pot synthesis of novel N-benzimidazolyl- α -arylnitrones catalyzed by salts of transition metals. *RSC advances*, 9(71), 41851-41860. DOI: 10.1039/C9RA08570J
8. Srivastava, M., Singh, K., Kumar, S., Hasan, S. M., Mujeeb, S., Kushwaha, S. P., & Husen, A. (2024) In silico Approaches for Exploring the Pharmacological Activities of Benzimidazole Derivatives: A Comprehensive Review. *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 24(16), 1481-1495. <https://doi.org/10.2174/0113895575287322240115115125>
9. Hernández-López, H., Tejada-Rodríguez, C. J., & Leyva-Ramos, S. (2022) A panoramic review of benzimidazole derivatives and their potential biological activity. *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 22(9), 1268-1280. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1389557522666220104150051>
10. Nardi, M., Cano, N. C. H., Simeonov, S., Bence, R., Kurutos, A., Scarpelli, R., & Procopio, A. (2023) A review on the green synthesis of benzimidazole derivatives and their pharmacological activities. *Catalysts*, 13(2), 392. <https://doi.org/10.3390/catal13020392>
11. Singh, H., Kumar, R., Tiwari, P., & Singh, A. (2022) Recent advances in synthetic strategies of benzimidazole and its analogs: A review. *Current Organic Chemistry*, 26(19), 1767-1778. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1385272827666221216113723>
12. Azam, M., Khan, A. A., Al-Resayes, S. I., Islam, M. S., Saxena, A. K., Dwivedi, S., & Kruszynski, R. (2015) Synthesis and characterization of 2-substituted benzimidazoles and their evaluation as anticancer agent. *Spectrochimica Acta Part A: Molecular and Biomolecular Spectroscopy*, 142, 286-291. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.saa.2015.01.106>
13. Anand, K., & Wakode, S. (2018) Synthesis, characterization and biological evaluation of benzimidazole derivatives. *International Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences and Research*, 9(2), 617-624. [http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.9\(2\).617-24](http://dx.doi.org/10.13040/IJPSR.0975-8232.9(2).617-24)

14. Ganie, A. M., Dar, A. M., Khan, F. A., & Dar, B. A. (2019) Benzimidazole derivatives as potential antimicrobial and antiulcer agents: A mini review. *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 19(16), 1292-1297.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1381612824666181017102930>
15. Nguyen, T. V., Peszko, M. T., Melander, R. J., & Melander, C. (2019) Using 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives to inhibit *Mycobacterium smegmatis* biofilm formation. *Medicinal Chemistry Communications*, 10(3), 456-459.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C9MD00025A>
16. Bansal, Y., Kaur, M., & Bansal, G. (2019) Antimicrobial potential of benzimidazole derived molecules. *Mini Reviews in Medicinal Chemistry*, 19(8), 624-646.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1389557517666171101104024>
17. Tan, Y., Leonhard, M., Moser, D., Ma, S., & Schneider-Stickler, B. (2019) Antibiofilm efficacy of curcumin in combination with 2-aminobenzimidazole against single-and mixed-species biofilms of *Candida albicans* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. *Colloids and Surfaces B: Biointerfaces*, 174, 28-34.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.colsurfb.2018.10.079>
18. Kanwal, A., Ahmad, M., Aslam, S., Naqvi, S. A. R., & Saif, M. J. (2019) Recent advances in antiviral benzimidazole derivatives: a mini review. *Pharmaceutical Chemistry Journal*, 53(3), 179-187.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11094-019-01976-3>
19. Kharitonova, M. I., Denisova, A. O., Andronova, V. L., Kayushin, A. L., Konstantinova, I. D., Kotovskaya, S. K., ... & Miroshnikov, A. I. (2017) New modified 2-aminobenzimidazole nucleosides: Synthesis and evaluation of their activity against herpes simplex virus type 1. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry Letters*, 27(11), 2484-2487.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmcl.2017.03.100>
20. Devine, S. M., Challis, M. P., Kigotho, J. K., Siddiqui, G., De Paoli, A., MacRaild, C. A., . & Scammells, P. J. (2021) Discovery and development of 2-aminobenzimidazoles as potent antimalarials. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 221, 113518.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2021.113518>
21. Hsu, M. J., Chen, H. K., Chen, C. Y., Lien, J. C., Gao, J. Y., Huang, Y. H., & Huang, S. W. (2022) Anti-angiogenic and anti-lymphangiogenic effects of a novel 2-aminobenzimidazole derivative, MFB. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, 862326.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.862326>
22. Lien, J. C., Chung, C. L., Huang, T. F., Chang, T. C., Chen, K. C., Gao, G. Y., ... & Huang, S. W. (2019) A novel 2-aminobenzimidazole-based compound Jzu 17 exhibits anti-angiogenesis effects by targeting VEGFR-2 signalling. *British Journal of Pharmacology*, 176(20), 4034-4049.
<https://doi.org/10.1111/bph.14813>
23. Chaouiki, A., Chafiq, M., Rbaa, M., Salghi, R., Lakhrissi, B., Ali, I. H., ... & Chung, I. M. (2020) Comprehensive assessment of corrosion inhibition mechanisms of novel benzimidazole compounds for mild steel in HCl: An experimental and theoretical investigation. *Journal of Molecular Liquids*, 320, 114383.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molliq.2020.114383>
24. Yu, X., Kan, J., Han, J., Liu, K., Li, J., Zhang, H., & Chen, J. (2024) Synthesis, scale and corrosion inhibition evaluation and mechanism of 2-aminobenzimidazole modified polyaspartic acid. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 12(3), 112950.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jece.2024.112950>
25. Townsend, L. B., & Drach, J. C. U.S. Patent No. 5,646,125. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office 1997. WO/1994/008456

26. Cook, C. M. (1996) Synthesis of symmetric and unsymmetric disulfides. The University of Texas at Arlington ProQuest Dissertations & Theses, 9707812.
27. Badawey, E. S. A., & Kappe, T. (1997) Synthesis and in vitro anti-HIV Activity of Certain 2-(1H-Benzimidazol-2-ylamino)pyrimidin-4 (3H)-ones and Related Derivatives. *Archiv der Pharmazie*, 330(3), 59-62.
<https://doi.org/10.1002/ardp.19973300304>
28. Index, M. An encyclopedia of Chemicals, Drugs and Biologicals 12th edition., Merck and Co. INC, USA 1996, 8697. DOI: 10.1021/jm068049o
29. Nawrocka, W. (1996) Syntheses and pharmacological properties of new 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives. *Bollettino Chimico Farmaceutico*, 135(1), 18-23. PMID: 9004736
30. Iriepa, I., Gil-Alberdi, B., Gálvez, E., Villasante, F. J., Bellanato, J., & Carmona, P. (1999) Synthesis, structural, conformational and pharmacological study of some carbamates derived from 3-methyl-2, 4-diphenyl-3-azabicyclo [3.3. 1] nonan-9 β -ol. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 482, 437-442.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2860\(98\)00947-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-2860(98)00947-8)
31. Vigorita, M. G., Previtiera, T., Zappalà, C., Trovato, A., Monforte, M. T., Barbera, R., & Pizzimenti, F. (1990) N-trifluoroacetyl derivatives as pharmacological agents. V. Evaluation of antiinflammatory and antimicrobial activities of some N-heterocyclic trifluoroacetamides. *Farmaco (Societa Chimica Italiana: 1989)*, 45(2), 223-235. PMID: 2133997
32. Nawrocka, W., Sztuba, B., Kowalska, M. W., Liszkiewicz, H., Wietrzyk, J., Nasulewicz, A., & Opolski, A. (2004) Synthesis and antiproliferative activity in vitro of 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives. *Farmaco*, 59(2), 83-91.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.farmac.2003.12.001>
33. Motghare, A., & Katolkar, p. (2022) Synthesis, reactions, and pharmacological applications of 2-aminobenzimidazoles: an update. *Synthesis*, 15(7). DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22159/ajpcr.2022v15i7.44899>
34. Daswani, U., Dubey, N., Sharma, P., & Kumar, A. (2016) A new NBS/oxone promoted one pot cascade synthesis of 2-aminobenzimidazoles/2-aminobenzoxazoles: a facile approach. *New Journal of Chemistry*, 40(9), 8093-8099.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C6NJ00478D>
35. Xie, Y., Zhang, F., Li, J., & Shi, X. (2010) Novel synthesis of 2-aminobenzimidazoles from isoselenocyanates. *Synlett* (06), 901-904. DOI: 10.1055/s-0029-1219395
36. Perkins, J. J., Zartman, A. E., & Meissner, R. S. (1999) Synthesis of 2-(alkylamino) benzimidazoles. *Tetrahedron letters*, 40(6), 1103-1106.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4039\(98\)02592-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0040-4039(98)02592-1)
37. Yang, L. (2022) Design, Synthesis, and antifungal activity of novel benzimidazole derivatives bearing thioether and carbamate moieties. *Journal of Chemistry*, (1), 8646557.
<https://doi.org/10.1155/2022/8646557>
38. Yadav, U. R., Devender, K., Poornima, M., Sekhar, C. C., Atcha, K. R., Reddy, B. S., & Padmaja, P. (2024) Design, synthesis and biological evaluation of triazole, sulfonamide and sulfonyl urea derivatives of N-acylhomoserine lactone as quorum sensing inhibitors. *Journal of Molecular Structure*, 1295, 136547.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.molstruc.2023.136547>
39. Huggins, W. M., Nguyen, T. V., Hahn, N. A., Baker, J. T., Kuo, L. G., Kaur, D., ... & Melander, C. (2018) 2-Aminobenzimidazoles as antibiofilm agents against *Salmonella enterica* serovar Typhimurium. *Medchemcomm*, 9(9), 1547-1552.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/C8MD00298C>

40. Saldivia, M., Fang, E., Ma, X., Myburgh, E., Carnielli, J. B., Bower-Lepts, C., & Rao, S. P. (2020) Targeting the trypanosome kinetochore with CLK1 protein kinase inhibitors. *Nature Microbiology*, 5(10), 1207-1216.
<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41564-020-0745-6>
41. Ferreira, R. A. A., Junior, C. D. O. R., Martinez, P. D. G., Koovits, P. J., Soares, B. M., Ferreira, L. L., & Dias, L. C. (2021) 2-aminobenzimidazoles for leishmaniasis: From initial hit discovery to in vivo profiling. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 15(2), e0009196.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.009196>
42. Mor, M., Bordi, F., Silva, C., Rivara, S., Zuliani, V., Vacondio, F., & Plazzi, P. V. (2004) Synthesis, biological activity, QSAR and QSPR study of 2-aminobenzimidazole derivatives as potent H3-antagonists. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 12(4), 663-674.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2003.11.030>
43. Devine, S. M., Challis, M. P., Kigotho, J. K., Siddiqui, G., De Paoli, A., MacRaild, C. A., & Scammells, P. J. (2021) Discovery and development of 2-aminobenzimidazoles as potent antimalarials. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 221, 113518.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2021.113518>
44. McNamara, N., Rahmani, R., Sykes, M. L., Avery, V. M., & Baell, J. (2020) Hit-to-lead optimization of novel benzimidazole phenylacetamides as broad spectrum trypanosomacides. *RSC Medicinal Chemistry*, 11(6), 685-695.
<https://doi.org/10.1039/D0MD00058B>
45. Júnior, C. D. O. R., Martinez, P. D. G., Ferreira, R. A. A., Koovits, P. J., Soares, B. M., Ferreira, L. L., & Dias, L. C. (2023) Hit-to-lead optimization of a 2-aminobenzimidazole series as new candidates for chagas disease. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 246, 114925.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2022.114925>
46. Ferreira, R. A. A., Junior, C. D. O. R., Martinez, P. D. G., Koovits, P. J., Soares, B. M., Ferreira, L. L., & Dias, L. C. (2021) 2-aminobenzimidazoles for leishmaniasis: From initial hit discovery to in vivo profiling. *PLoS Neglected Tropical Diseases*, 15(2), e0009196.
<https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pntd.009196>
47. Francesconi, V., Rizzo, M., Schenone, S., Carbone, A., & Tonelli, M. (2024) State-of-the-art review on the antiparasitic activity of benzimidazolebased derivatives: facing malaria, leishmaniasis, and trypanosomiasis. *Current Medicinal Chemistry*, 31(15), 1955-1982.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/0929867331666230915093928>
48. Hsu, M. J., Chen, H. K., Chen, C. Y., Lien, J. C., Gao, J. Y., Huang, Y. H., ... & Huang, S. W. (2022) Anti-angiogenetic and anti-lymphangiogenic effects of a novel 2-aminobenzimidazole derivative, MFB. *Frontiers in Oncology*, 12, 862326.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fonc.2022.862326>
49. Zubair, A. M., Malik, M. N. H., Younis, W., Malik, M. A. H., Jahan, S., Ahmed, I., & Imran, A. (2022) Novel acetamide derivatives of 2-aminobenzimidazole prevent inflammatory arthritis in rats via suppression of pro-inflammatory mediators. *Inflammopharmacology*, 30(3), 1005-1019.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s10787-022-00969-1>
50. Padilla-Martínez, I. I., Cruz, A., García-Báez, E. V., Rosales-Hernández, M. C., & Mendieta Wejebe, J. E. (2023). N-substitution reactions of 2-aminobenzimidazoles to access pharmacophores. *Current Organic Synthesis*, 20(2), 177-219.
<https://doi.org/10.2174/1570179419666220310124223>

51. Zhu, J., Wu, C. F., Li, X., Wu, G. S., Xie, S., Hu, Q. N., & Hong, X. (2013) Synthesis, biological evaluation and molecular modeling of substituted 2-aminobenzimidazoles as novel inhibitors of acetylcholinesterase and butyrylcholinesterase. *Bioorganic & Medicinal Chemistry*, 21(14), 4218-4224. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.bmc.2013.05.001>
52. Spasov, A. A., Zhukovskaya, O. N., Gurova, N. A., Naumenko, L. V., Eliseeva, N. V., Kucheryavenko, A. F., & Morkovnik, A. S. (2022) Pharmacological Properties of 2-Aminobenzimidazole Halides and Imidazo [1, 2-a] Benzimidazole Derivatives. *Russian Journal of Bioorganic Chemistry*, 48(2), 281-291. <https://doi.org/10.1134/S1068162022020236>
53. Nawrocka, W., & Zimecki, M. (1998) Synthesis and Immunotropic Activity of Some 2-Aminobenzimidazoles, Part 4. *Archiv der Pharmazie: An International Journal Pharmaceutical and Medicinal Chemistry*, 331(7-8), 249-253. [https://doi.org/10.1002/\(SICI\)1521-4184\(199807\)331](https://doi.org/10.1002/(SICI)1521-4184(199807)331:7<249::AID-ARND249>3.0.CO;2-1)
54. Sørensen, U. S., Strøbæk, D., Christophersen, P., Hougaard, C., Jensen, M. L., Nielsen, E. & Teuber, L. (2008) Synthesis and structure activity relationship studies of 2-(N-substituted)-aminobenzimidazoles as potent negative gating modulators of small conductance Ca²⁺-activated K⁺ channels. *Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 51(23), 7625-7634. <https://doi.org/10.1021/jm800809f>
55. Yu, J., Niu, Y., Sun, Q., Xu, F., Liang, L., Wang, C., & Xu, P. (2017) Design and synthesis of 2-aminobenzimidazoles as potential BACE1 inhibitors. *Journal of Chinese Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 26(9), 650. <https://doi.org/10.5246/jcps.2017.09.073>
56. Bywater, W. G., McGinty, D. A., & Jenesel, N. D. Antithyroid studies: II. (1945) The goitrogenic activity of some imidazoles and benzimidazoles. *The Journal of Pharmacology and Experimental Therapeutics*, 85(1), 14-22. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3565\(25\)07884-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0022-3565(25)07884-X)
57. Rastogi, R., & Sharma, S. (1983) 2-Aminobenzimidazoles in organic syntheses. *Synthesis*, 1983(11), 861-882. <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.joc.3c02212>
58. Devine, S. M., Challis, M. P., Kigotho, J. K., Siddiqui, G., De Paoli, A., MacRaild, C. A., & Scammells, P. J. (2021) Discovery and development of 2-aminobenzimidazoles as potent antimalarials. *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, 221, 113518. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmech.2021.113518>